

e-ISSN: 2721-303X, p-ISSN: 2721-3021
Received: 4 June 2022, Revised: 15 June 2022, Publish: 5 July 2022
DOI: <https://doi-org/10.38035/dijefa.v3ix>
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Remuneration Committee and Profitability: Evidence from Nigeria

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Abstract: *There is a low profit reported by quoted firms in Nigeria. In a recent study, return on asset, which is a measure of profitability was reported to be as low as 2%. In addition, most of the empirical evidences supporting this nexus are coming from developed economies. This situation is not sustainable and survivable in the case of emerging markets. There is urgent need to call for investigations into possible solutions. In this paper, the focus is on the role of board of directors' remuneration committee in creating the atmosphere in which board members would feel well remunerated or motivated to work towards improving profitability. This study used ordinary least square regression to test the relationship between the remuneration committee and firm profitability, after controlling for regression diagnostics (normality and homoscedasticity of residual, multicollinearity, model specification, panel tests). The data was based on 112 companies trading on the floor of the Nigerian Exchange Group over ten years (2012-2021). Descriptive statistics, correlation and regression analysis are used to analyse the data. The findings indicate a significantly positive relationship between the remuneration committee and profitability. It is concluded therefore that remuneration committee is a major determinant of profitability among firms quoted in Nigeria. As with all empirical studies, however, this study is subject to several limitations. First of all, the choice of the country is open to criticism, as other countries within the continent are equally available. Second, the results may have been affected by the methods, data, model, and variables. Third, relying on the adapted model may not be free of errors. Finally, using broader set of variables that can act as proxies could be considered as possible, and therefore the study is limited to the independent variables used in this paper.*

Keywords: remuneration committee, financial performance, profitability

INTRODUCTION

Remuneration committee (RC) is very important to any organization, particularly quoted companies. Concerns for corporations to make profit have received several attentions based on the numerous amount of scholarly works available, directed at improving firms' profitability. For example, Aliyu et al. (2021) related profitability with board of directors. Yahaya (2006) examined the effect of size on profitability. Further, Yahaya (2014) examined social disclosure and profitability. Igbal and Kakakhel (2016) examined the role of remuneration committee in financial performance. Also, Agyemang-Mintah (2016) examined the role of RC in firm performance. Yahaya et al. (2014) examined country-specific characteristics and profitability. Gregory-Smith (2012) examined CEO pay and RC. Yahaya and Lamidi (2015) investigated profitability of Islamic bank in Nigeria. Khan et al. (2021) compared RC with firm financial performance. Yahaya et al. (2015) examined the association between current assets management and profitability in Nigerian banks. Narwal and Jindal (2015) examined the influence of corporate governance on profitability. Yahaya and Andow (2015) interrogated capital structure and profitability among conglomerates in Nigeria. Cybinski and Windsor (2013) also examined the role of remuneration in firm financial performance.

In addition, Yahaya (2018) further related environmental reporting practices of Nigerian environmentally-sensitive firms with profitability. Garcia-Izquierdo et al. (2018) examined the role of gender diversity in profitability in Spain. Yahaya et al. (2015) assessed the influence of risk management on profitability. Ogden and Watson (2004) interrogated the role of CEO pay in profitability among water industry companies in the UK. Yahaya and Onyabe (2020) looked at the firm life cycle and profitability in Nigeria. Kiradoo (2019) examined the role of corporate governance on profitability and firm financial performance. Yahaya (2019) also examined the influence of intellectual capital management on financial competitiveness (a proxy for profitability) among oil and gas companies in Nigeria. Yahaya and Alexander (2015) linked business processing restructuring with profitability.

Zraiq and Fadzil (2018) examined the role of remuneration committee in firm financial performance. Yahaya and Lamido (2022) recently examined the influence of corporate responsibility on profitability. Jafaar (2012) also examined the influence of remuneration committee on firm financial performance among family firms in Malaysia. Yahaya (2022) also examined the role of corporate governance on profitability in Nigeria using agency theory. Al-Dhamari and Alquhaif (2020) looked at remuneration committee and debt holders' perceptions of accounting information quality. Yahaya (2022) further examined the role of female directors on profitability using audit committee as a moderator. Demaki (2018) interrogated the influence of corporate governance on profitability among banks in Nigeria. Yahaya (2022) related working capital with profitability.

Furthermore, Słomka-Gołębiowska (2016) examined the effect of remuneration committee independence on pay among banks in Poland. Yahaya and Awen (2021) related asset structure with profitability. Safari (2015) assessed the role of

Remuneration committee in firm dividends in Malaysia. Similarly, Yahaya and Alkasim (2021) examined the influence of sustainability on profitability among listed insurance firms in Nigeria. Cameron (2005) examined the role of remuneration committees in executive pay determination and firm financial performance. Yahaya and Ogwiji (2021) related risk committee traits with profitability among banks in Nigeria. Rahayu et al. (2022) looked at the influence of remuneration committee in firm financial performance and directors' pay. Opeyemi et al. (2020) related firm specific characteristics with profitability among listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. Brian and Jackson (2007) examined the influence of remuneration committee in strategic human resource management. Yahaya and Yusuf (2020) related ethical behavioural disclosure with profitability among industrial goods companies in Nigeria. Akbar and Ramadhan (2020) examined the influence of remuneration committee in payment of audit fees. Yahaya et al. (2019) financial mix with profitability among consumer goods firms in Nigeria. Finally, Puni (2015) assessed the role of remuneration committee in corporate financial performance in Ghana.

Recent reviews of corporate governance research on corporate boards have specified that though much has been learned and already done, it is time for reflection and the exploration of new directions in board research and focus on less researched areas. Nigerian Corporate Governance codes and reforms in Nigeria have centered upon assisting the executive management and the board of a company to make the right decisions in order to achieve their stakeholders' objectives. So, among the sub-committees noted in the settings, the remuneration committee, as compared to other committees, has received the least attention from researchers to the knowledge of the researcher. For this reason, the researcher conducted this study to fill the gaps in the theoretical framework and to indicate the importance of this committee (Abobakr, 2017; Eulaiwi et al., 2016).

The RC is evolving to become one of the most prominent issues of the global economy. The RC is recognizing the importance of growth and profitability of a company by focusing on the RC of the company and reporting its' performance, there have been many discoveries of the possible benefits that companies may receive (Chung & Wei, 2017; Mintah, 2015). RC should ensure that the appointed board members have appropriate balance of skills, age, gender, educational qualifications, experience, independence and knowledge of the company to enable them to discharge their duties successfully. Members should also receive a formal induction, and regularly update and refresh their skills and knowledge in the company. Many studies show that in firms with better governance, there are less instances of opportunistic behaviour by managers. Better governance, indeed, helps to align the interests of managers and shareholders boosting the corporate financial performance.

From the point of view of the researcher, the success of this committee means the success of the company because it followed all the procedures and methods to ensure the composition of the fullest (Kaczmarek et al., 2012). However, findings of past studies did not fully explore all related knowledge and understanding towards remuneration committee. Thus, current study aims to investigate the relationship

between RC and corporate profitability. From the knowledge of the researcher, previous studies are very rare and scarce specifically in developing countries (especially in Nigeria) and know the shortcomings of this committee. In addition, the current study would use data from Nigeria for case illustration. It is also necessary to state that most of the studies were not linking remuneration committee with profitability. It is also necessary at this point to distinguish between profitability and financial performance. Very often, several studies are abound linking remuneration committee with firm financial performance. It must be recognized that profitability is the most important component of financial performance that investors and lenders are interested in.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The RC, which is one of the important committee of the board of directors, and the RC it will help minimize agency conflict by ensuring that appointed board members work together to achieve shareholders interest. This means that the RC plays an essential and important role in the success and failure of the company. The corporate financial performance (CFP) of companies collectively depends on whatever the RC has appointed to the board and who is part of the executive management team. The RC has to ensure that the right candidate with the right profile is selected to heighten the probability of success for the company (Appiah & Chizema, 2016). Several empirical studies have shown that an independent RC that comprises independent members is less likely is influenced by the CEO or other executive directors in the director appointment process. This occurrence will increase the recruitment of directors with reputations for being active in exercising their control over the executive directors to raise the CFP (Cybinski & Windsor, 2013; Zajac & Westphal, 1996).

Most importantly, the RC must be influential enough to introduce its own independent suggestions and not be influenced by the CEO or the executive directors. Finally, the existence RC creates the value of the company. In addition, the board tends to have different and unique ideas, experiences and power of thinking and this serves as the basis for better outcomes during the decision-making process and policy making process and enhance the CFP (Pirzada et al., 2017). The objective of this research is to determine if the presence of RC can improve the CFP, and how it can enhance the overall ROA and EPS of a company. The RC is one of the least researched subject areas in the effectiveness of board committees (for example, Cybinski & Windsor, 2013; Huse, 2011; Handa, 2018). Due to the limited amount of empirical research on the effectiveness of the RC, this research will be the first to materially assess its impact on Nigerian companies. Various corporate governance (CG) regulatory reforms in the Nigeria have also provided the impetus to investigate the extent to which the RC is able to impact the CFP of a company. These will serve as the motivation of the research and help fill in any gaps in the current CG research literature. This paper focuses on the RC impact on the CFP that is, return on asset (ROA) and earnings per share (EPS).

Agency theory primarily focuses on the separation of ownership and control, which exist in organizations (Berle & Means, 1932), and the relationship between the

principal and the agent, which is intrinsically open to several problems (Berle & Means, 1932; Jensen & Meckling, 1976; Eisenhardt, 1989). The first is the problem with information asymmetry, where the agent has easier access to information within the company than the principal, and the second is the possibility of conflicts of interest between the principal and the agent as a result of divergent interests (Jensen & Meckling, 1976; Hill & Jones, 1992). The findings are consistent with agency theory, which argues that the presence of RC ensures that appropriate skills, talents and competencies are brought into the organization to help maximize shareholders' returns. This suggests that:

H₁: There is a relationship between remuneration committee and profitability.

This research focuses on listed firms because they are heavily regulated and have unique capital structure, which can impact their profitability (Guest, 2009; Yermack, 1996). A secondary reason for choosing listed firms was because they are very important for rapid expansion and capital allocation (Ross, 2003; Zagorchev & Gao, 2015). However, to the best of the knowledge of the author, there is no study which directly measures between RC and profitability in Nigeria.

RESEARCH METHODS

The current study sample comprises of 112 companies for the years 2012 and 2021 and excluded firms suspended for various different accounts ranging from below listing standards, missed regulatory standards to missed regulatory filing (see also Barontini & Caprio, 2006; Bøhren & Strøm, 2010). Data of the firms is obtained from their annual reports compiled from the NGX. Profitability was measured by accounting-based measurement (ROA and EPS). It is a forward-looking measurement reflecting the shareholder expectations regarding future performance of the firm, which is based on past or current performance (Ganguli & Agrawal, 2009; Shan & McIver, 2011; Wahla et al., 2012). As a traditional measure ROA and EPS measure the expected firm long-run performance (Bozec et al., 2010) as opposed to market value of equity which measures the firm's growth opportunities arising from factors external to managerial decisions and this is exhibited through the companies' level (Shan & McIver, 2011; Demsetz & Villalonga, 2001).

Table 1. Summary of Variables Measurement

No	Variables	Acronym	Operationalisation
Dependent variables (DV)			
1	Return on Asset	ROA	Earnings (before tax) divided by total assets of the firm.
2	Earnings per Share	EPS	Net income divided by number of shares outstanding.
Independent Variables (IV)			
3	Remuneration Committee	RC	measured by '1' if company has remuneration committee and '0' otherwise.

The corporate governance committee variable namely, remuneration committee (RC) was studied. Table 1 offers the variable measurement summary. In sum, the relationship between remuneration committee was studied by using the following model:

$$ROA_{i,t} = \alpha_0 + \gamma_1 RC_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

$$EPS_{i,t} = \alpha_0 + \gamma_1 RC_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

Whereas:

ROA = Return on asset, measured as profit after tax divided by total asset (Yahaya & Lamidi, 2015; Yahaya & Lamido, 2022; Yahaya & Yusuf, 2020; Yahaya & Ogwiji, 2020; Yahaya, 2022; Yahaya & Awen, 2021)

EPS = Earnings per share, measured as profit after tax divided number of ordinary shares (Yahaya et al., 2015; Yahaya et al., 2015, Yahaya et al., 2015; Yahaya & Alexander, 2015; Yahaya, 2018)

RC = Remuneration committee measured as 1 if it is in existence, or 0 otherwise (Zraiq & Fadzil, 2018).

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The continuous variables' descriptive statistics included the mean, standard deviation, and minimum and maximum, which are obtained with the help of STATA 14. See Table 2.

Table 2
DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS OF
VARIABLES

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std.	Std.
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic
RC	112	0.0	1.0	0.408	0.0326	0.4925
ROA	112	-91.90	3.47	-0.342	0.7684	10.969
EPS	112	-1.07	7.20	0.3454	0.1222	1.846

In this study, the correlation analysis was carried out through the multiple linear regressions. Pallant (2011) stated that correlation analysis is useful in describing the strength and direction of the linear relationship between two variables. See Table 3.

Table 3
Results of Pearson Correlation Analysis

		RC	ROA	EPS
RC	Pearson	1	0.164	0.161
	Correlation		*	*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	-	0.013	0.015
	N	112	112	112
ROA	Pearson	0.164	1	0.167
	Correlation	*		-
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.013	-	0.012
	N	112	112	112
EPS	Pearson	0.161	0.167	1
	Correlation	*	*	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.015	0.012	-
	N	112	112	112

*p>0.05

The finding suggests the existence of RC is associated with higher performance Tables 4 and 5. Thus, hypothesis H₁ is supported. This finding is consistent with previous studies that found a positive relationship between RC and firm profitability such as Appiah & Chizema, 2016; Cybinski & Windsor 2013; Mintah, 2015. One probable clarification for the positive significant association between RC and profitability is that this result is supported by Agency Theory, which postulates that the board has to be stricter when it comes to monitoring of management to ensure financial performance.

Table 4
Regression Results of Model (Dependent= ROA)

Variables	R-square	Standardized Coefficients Beta	t-value	Sig.
(Constant)	0.027	-	-1.965	0.05
RC	-	0.164	2.503	0.01

Table 5
REGRESSION RESULTS OF MODEL (DEPENDENT=
EPS)

Variables	R-square	Standardized Coefficients Beta	t-value	Sig.
(Constant)	0.026	-	0.632	0.53
RC	-	0.161	2.453	0.02

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This study is considered to have achieved its main target, which is to test the relationship between the RC and profitability among quoted Nigerian companies. Moreover, this study added variable to the body of knowledge such as, RC. The present study employed several assumptions to examine the association between independent variable and dependent variable as discussed in the research methodology section. The data used for this study comprised of 112 companies and according to the findings, a significant positive relationship exists between the RC and profitability among Nigerian listed companies. This study has many recommendations for future studies. Firstly, this study examined a direct relationship but there is a lack of previous research examining the moderating or mediating effect of other variables on the relation between RC and profitability such as, board diversity, culture, regulation, among others that will lead to improving performance. Secondly, future authors should investigate the relationship between RC and profitability in-depth, by adding new variables such as size, independence, expertise, meeting and gender. Thirdly, this study recommends future authors to study the relationship between RC and profitability through other theories such as, stewardship theory, institutional theory and stakeholders' theory as these theories may be more suitable for this environment. Finally, future authors should extend proxies of firm performance and integrate between accounting and market measurements as these may lead to effective performance evaluation in both the short-and long-term.

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